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10 **Fostering Creativity as a Problem-Solving Competence through Design:** 11 **Think-Create-Learn, a Tool for Teachers**

12 **Abstract**

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15 Although there is no doubt about the relevance of creativity within education, theory has not been
16 always translated into the practical level, for many reasons. In this paper we analyse the state of art,
17 studying the methods through which creativity is understood and applied by teachers, and identifying
18 problems and opportunities. Accordingly, we conducted a literature review to identify what should
19 be considered to foster creativity in classrooms; from this review, we define fifteen key indicators of
20 creativity in education: incorporation, practicality, novel, atmosphere, stimulation, analysis,
21 cooperation, intrinsic motivation, participation, flexibility, uncertainty, time, divergence, self-
22 evaluation, and redefinition. Based on these indicators, we provide a methodological proposal and a
23 set of practical resources to help the teacher to encourage creativity in any classroom. ‘Think-Create-
24 Learn’ relies on open, accessible, and intuitive design-based tools, facing challenges through a
25 creative, problem-solving approach; connecting the contents with the student’s interests and reality;
26 and generating new competency learning possibilities. The assessment of the methodology, with
27 teachers and students, demonstrates its positive integration into the lines of current teaching
28 curriculums, its validity to support mentioned factors, and its ability to aid teachers to produce more
29 creative people. In short, this paper evidences how design discipline and the methodology proposed
30 could have a relevant role in the creativity development inside educational centres.
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33 **Keywords:** Creativity; Design Thinking; Didactics; Methodology; Teaching Skills

34 **1. Introduction**

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37 Decades ago, Guilford (1950) wondered why the schools failed to produce ‘more creative people’
38 and, finally, creativity has been considered one of the most important 21st century thinking skills
39 (Ahmadi et al., 2019; Collard & Looney, 2014; Guo & Woulfin, 2016; Henriksen et al., 2016;
40 Mishra & Mehta, 2017; Nakano & Wechsler, 2018). But do we really know how to develop and
41 promote it? Has the theory been translated into the practical level?
42

43 Creativity is an essentially combinatorial process; it is the ability to connect learned knowledge to
44 solve problems and create new things (Kleiman, 2008). Thus, it allows society to advance, looking
45 beyond the established ways, answering to the changing world, and increasing the quality of life (De
46 Bono & Castillo, 1994; Hernández-Torrano & Ibrayeva, 2020; Spendlove, 2008). Creativity tends to
47 be related to problem-solving because ‘the two share many processes’ (Reiter-Palmon & Illies,
48 2004). Although there is a debate about their exact relationship (Kirton, 2004; Parkhurst, 1999), there

49 are authors that understand that creativity is promoted by problem-solving (Fasko, 2001; Feldhusen
50 & Treffinger, 1985; Guilford, 1967; Khalid et al., 2020) and that requires a cognitive process away
51 from luck or divine spark (Howard et al., 2008).

52

53 Our point of departure is that creativity is not a talent limited to some people but is present in all
54 humans, to a greater or lesser extent (Collard & Looney, 2014; Guilford, 1950), and that to awake,
55 stimulate, and develop this potential requires training in a favourable environment (Burkus, 2013;
56 López, 2008). Obviously, the educational environment has a key role in this matter: people spend a
57 lot of time there, and it reaches all kind of social classes (Chan & Yuen, 2014; Davies et al., 2013;
58 Shaheen, 2010). In fact, for many, it should be transversally embedded within the whole curriculum
59 of the educational programs (Daly et al., 2014; Fasko, 2001), being present in four pillars: educator,
60 student, environment, and methodological resources (López, 2008). In this way, the learning
61 environment could favour student's own development, boosting productivity, adaptability, and
62 efficiency (Craft, 2003; Davies et al., 2013; Simonton, 2000).

63

64 It is true that a few years ago, a change in education policy began to spread throughout the world
65 with the objective of combining creativity and knowledge as an engine of school improvement
66 (Burnard, 2006; Collard & Looney, 2014; Dickhut, 2003). Creativity has transformed into one of the
67 curriculum and pedagogy spotlights (Wilson, 2005) at several educational levels, from the early
68 years to primary education for most countries and up to higher education, for some of them
69 (Shaheen, 2010).

70

71 Unfortunately, although there is no doubt that interest in creativity within education has increased, in
72 practice, it remains difficult to achieve, and it is often reduced as a separate area from other
73 educational objectives (Spendlove, 2008). This is caused by barriers of widely varied natures,
74 complex and difficult to address for educators (Henriksen et al., 2017).

75

76 Perhaps one of the biggest problems is the strong prevalence of the traditional methods of teaching
77 that still exist in formal education, both in public or private schools, and at all educational levels.
78 Methodology is based on the student as a blank slate onto which information is etched by the
79 teacher; on the use of conferences and passive learning, where students listen or watch how the
80 instructor solves problems; and on the textbooks. Some factors that may influence the prevalence of
81 traditional methodologies are the teacher profile (age, motivation/vocation, personal situation), as
82 well as on the administrative structure of the educational centres — in terms of resources availability,
83 restricted hours, class size, comfort, time constraints, and level of communication and joint work
84 among teachers (Lee & Erdogan, 2007; McMullan, 2016; Nguyen et al., 2017; Qi, 2017; Zhang &
85 Guo, 2017; Zhao & Meng, 2015).

86

87 Another important factor is that, as a knowledge area, creativity is a multifaceted, and a relatively
88 new and unknown activity. As López (2008) highlighted, '*Creativity aims to promote the divergent
89 in a converged environment; the indefinite in a system that aims to transmit the defined and known*',
90 hence placing the educator in an uncertain position. Also, the term 'creativity' is sometimes used
91 incorrectly; creativity and imagination are used interchangeably (Craft, 2002), and creativity is
92 linked, by default, to arts or leisure (Henriksen et al., 2017; Seltzer & Bentley, 1999). Additionally,
93 the term is surrounded by ingrained myths (Burkus, 2013; Cromptley, 2016; Cromptley, 2018; MacLaren,
94 2012) oblivious to the idea of creativity as a process.

95

96 Considering this background, the need is clear for practical solutions that help teachers to encourage
97 creativity in the classrooms. One of the knowledge areas that can have a very positive influence on

98 this task is the design field, and Design Thinking in its broadest sense. Creativity and design are
99 closely related, and many authors recognise Design Thinking, *per se*, as a creative process (Elwood
100 et al., 2016; Henriksen et al., 2017; Hernández-Leo et al., 2017; Jordan, 2016; Koehler & Mishra,
101 2005). Design thinking is an iterative process that repeatedly reformulates a problem to find its core
102 and then analyses possible solutions to find the most favourable, allowing for the formation of
103 ‘creative bridges’ between problems and solutions (Cross, 2011; Dorst & Cross, 2001). As Blanco
104 (2016) stated, ‘*the approach from the design represents a differential advantage, both for the*
105 *approach to the problem, and for the efficiency, affordability and adaptability of its tools*’. In this
106 sense, Design Thinking achieves a balance between convergent and divergent processes, both of
107 which are essential to develop transversal creative thinking skill (Elwood et al., 2016; Gu et al.,
108 2019; Hadar & Tirosh, 2019).

109
110 In the education field, Design Thinking can foster open-mindedness in students, create an effective
111 framework to promote creativity as a transversal element (Mosely et al., 2018; Page &
112 Thorsteinsson, 2017; Thorsteinsson & Page, 2017), and improve skills such as collaboration,
113 problem-solving, and innovation, among others (Brown, 2008; Razzouk & Shute, 2012). By
114 developing these skills, the student can achieve what is known as ‘creative confidence’ (Rauth et al.,
115 2010). Therefore, teachers should employ Design Thinking in their classrooms (Brown, 2008;
116 Carroll et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2020; Lor, 2017; Razzouk & Shute, 2012; Retna, 2016).

117
118 For these reasons, the need to support educators with tools and approaches from the point of view of
119 this discipline has been already detected (Elwood et al., 2016; Henriksen et al., 2017; Hernández Leo
120 et al., 2017; Hoogveld et al., 2005; Jordan, 2016; Norton & Hathaway, 2015; Retna, 2016). In this
121 sense, some initiatives have been launched; for example, Ideo (2013) provided some guidance for
122 teachers to design certain solutions, but focused on the schools’ facilities.

123
124 To address the problem, in the next sections of this paper, we present a methodology called Think-
125 Create-Learn (TCL). Section 2 shows the theoretical bases, stressing the training of more creative
126 individuals. Section 3 collects the results of TCL assessment, carried out in a real educational
127 environment with end users (teachers and students of 15 to 16 years old), by qualitative and
128 quantitative methods. Finally, Section 4 discusses TCL’s utility, the advantages, difficulties, and
129 limitations derived from its implementation, and the feedback necessary for its improvement.

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131 **2. Materials and Methods**

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133 As explained in the introduction, in order to develop a resource that encourages creativity in the
134 classroom, some challenges must be addressed, such as the frequent use of traditional educational
135 methodologies, the education system limitations, and the interpretation of the term ‘creativity’.

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137 **2.1 Theoretical Bases**

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139 Evidently, developing a resource that fosters creativity is not a direct task, and its purpose must be
140 based on a scientific approach. Therefore, the first step was to identify, as a theoretical basis, those
141 factors which influence the development of creativity. To accomplish this, we conducted a literature
142 search, in accordance to Lodico et al., (2010), employing ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, Libraries,
143 and ERIC. We used the term ‘creativity’ in combination with the terms ‘factors’, ‘aspects’,
144 ‘evaluation’, ‘theory’, ‘education’, ‘teaching’, and ‘materials’. As inclusion criteria, we selected
145 those publications that described creativity characteristics, how to introduce creativity in education,
146 or how to teach creativity.

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148 Under these criteria, from the title and the abstract, it was determined which studies met the inclusion
 149 criteria. In the selected publications, we identified ideas and concepts related to the creative process,
 150 which could be developed in the educational environment, and which defined key aspects for
 151 introducing and fostering creativity in classrooms. Despite not considering a specific field during the
 152 search, the authors of the selected publications turned out to be mostly from psychology and
 153 education fields. It is understandable, given the scope of the research, and also because we excluded
 154 those quotes that were directly related to other environments (e.g. business, industry). In any case,
 155 the fields of reviewed authors give an idea of the theoretical bases on which the determination of the
 156 factors is based. The next step in the process was based on taxonomic sorting method (Withers et al.,
 157 2014), specifically the open card sorting method (Spencer & Warfel, 2004). We wrote the selected
 158 quotes on sticky notes (cards) and placed them on a large blackboard. Then, we combined these
 159 cards to make conceptual and thematic groups, which were no pre-established. Finally, we named
 160 each group to describe the content. As a result, we isolated 15 thematic groups, which are the 15
 161 creativity factors shown in Table 1. The factors were organised according to the hypothetical
 162 sequence of use of teaching resources, and we collated them with colleagues from design and
 163 education field.

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165 **Table 1**166 *Creativity Factors*

Factor	Definition	References
1. Incorporation	It is adapted correctly to the curriculum	(Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; Finke et al., 1992; Logan et al., 1980; López, 2008; Şendurur et al., 2016; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997; Torre & Violant, 2006)
2. Practicality	The materials are logical, useful, and sensitive to the needs of the teacher and student	(Finke et al., 1992; López, 2008; Şendurur et al., 2016)
3. Novel	It is original and attractive	(Finke et al., 1992; Guilford, 1950; Huidobro & González, 2004; Şendurur et al., 2016; Simonton, 2000; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997; Torrance, 1972)
4. Atmosphere	It seeks to escape the monotonous, dogmatic, and traditional work	(Craft, 2003; Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; Gervilla, 2003; Lewis, 2009; Logan et al., 1980; López, 2008; Peterson, 2001)
5. Stimulation	It helps to awaken interest	(Craft, 2003; Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; Gervilla, 2003; González, 2006; Huidobro & González, 2004; Torre & Violant, 2006)
6. Analysis	The concepts are understood	(Hennessey & Amabile, 1987; Huidobro & González, 2004; Simonton, 2000)
7. Cooperation	It promotes communication and teamwork	(Amabile, 1998; Gervilla, 2003; Huidobro & González, 2004; Torre & Violant, 2006)
8. Intrinsic Motivation	Students are motivated in order to perform actions by themselves	(Amabile, 1998; Craft, 2003; González, 2006; Guilford, 1950; Huidobro & González, 2004; Logan et al., 1980; López, 2008; Simonton, 2000; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997; Torrance, 1972; Torre & Violant, 2006)
9. Participation	It encourages participation, welcoming opinions, questions, and answers	(Fasko, 2001; Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; Gervilla, 2003; González, 2006; Huidobro & González, 2004)
10. Flexibility	It allows changes or variations as required	(Finke et al., 1992; Gervilla, 2003; González, 2006; Guilford, 1950; Huidobro & González, 2004; Logan et al., 1980; Simonton, 2000; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997; Torrance, 1972; Torre & Violant, 2006)
11. Uncertainty	It fosters curiosity, inquiry, research, and	(Fasko, 2001; Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; Gervilla, 2003;

	experience and allows for making mistakes	González, 2006; Guilford, 1950; Hennessey & Amabile, 1987; Huidobro & González, 2004; Lewis, 2009; Logan et al., 1980; Peterson, 2001; Simonton, 2000; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997; Torrance, 1972)
12. Time	It allows time for reflection	(Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985)
13. Divergence	It allows for looking at things from different perspective to find more than one possible solution	(Feldhusen & Treffinger, 1985; González, 2006; Guilford, 1950; Huidobro & González, 2004; Simonton, 2000; Sternberg & Lubart, 1997)
14. Self-evaluation	It requires self-evaluation for reflection and enrichment	(Gervilla, 2003; Logan et al., 1980; Torre & Violant, 2006)
15. Redefinition	It requires the student to take feedback and redefine the problem/solution/etc.	(Gervilla, 2003; Guilford, 1950; Torrance, 1972)

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2.2 Methodology Rationale

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Despite the advantages of Design Thinking for students' education, as happens with creativity, its application in the classroom is not a straightforward labour. Thus, TCL has three fundamental bases: the 15 creativity factors, the adaptation of Design Thinking models, and the development of didactic materials. Additionally, we designed the methodology based on our experience in design and didactics, as well as on a collaborative approach between both disciplines. During the development of TCL, we closely cooperated with teachers from different training cycles; they provided feedback on and a full perspective of the educational environment.

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One of our first decisions was to order the phases of the methodology, which, as well as the factors, were organised from the general characteristics of didactic material to the specific impact of the material on the students. Figure 1 details the relationship between TCL phases (identified with different colours) with the creativity factors enhanced in each of them.

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The first and second phases are carried out individually by the teacher before the class; the first has a formative nature and the second an operative nature. The third phase constitutes the core of the action with the students in the classroom, and the fourth phase requires the student to reflect on their learning and allows for the dissemination of the results.

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The development of each phase was formed to materialise one or more creativity factors (see Figure 1). The first phase, 'Integrate', introduces the teacher to the theoretical basis of the methodology and identifies the initial creativity factors which are focused on adapting the materials into the environment. The second phase, 'Prepare', helps the teacher to set the operational resources. In this case, attention was given to provide enough flexibility to be adapted to each educator's needs. The third phase, 'Apply', implements the material in the classroom and fosters the development of the factors by the students. The evolution of this phase and its steps was inspired by the Design Thinking model 'Double Diamond'; the first diamond involves exploring an issue widely or deeply (divergent thinking) and then focusing on a challenge (convergent thinking), and the second diamond involves giving different answers to the challenge (divergent thinking) and then defining the solution (convergent thinking) (Design Council, 2005). Finally, the fourth phase, 'Assess', evaluates learning after the methodology application and allows for the student to reflect on their new knowledge. In this manner, the methodology considers assessment as a key part of the learning process.

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Overall, TCL aims to help teachers to apply Design Thinking in the classroom and is focused on transforming knowledge into solving challenges, all in order to foster creative ability in students and set new competency learning possibilities.

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Fig. 1. Think-Create-Learn methodology

2.3 Methodology Materials and Methodology Implementation

As mentioned in the introduction section, both the visual and the tactile nature of the materials are crucial in Design-Thinking processes. TCL is embodied in a practical kit (see Figure 2) that consists of three material types: a manual to teach by challenges, complementary templates to fill and follow the steps, and other tangible support materials. Every resource has a careful, simple appearance, adapted to both teachers and students.

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Fig. 2. Very first kit's physical prototype developed to assess TCL

The manual consists of 22 guide cards which explain to the teacher step-by-step how to use TCL in the classroom. Figure 3 shows a card example, where the structure and elements designed for consistency with the other materials are described.

The complementary templates are wide sheets that make application of theory possible (see supplementary files). Their main function is to save the teacher time in materials preparation and to optimise students' activities execution. They provide the added benefit of avoiding potential blocks caused by the fear of the blank page.

The support materials are tangible and colourful resources such as post-its, stickers, a stopwatch, markers, etc., aimed to facilitate students' work and to favour the activation of the right side of their brains.

Fig. 3. Card elements

Figure 4 depicts the methodology steps and relates them to the specific materials. The first three columns describe the materials mentioned above. Additionally, the fourth column includes how TCL was applied and assessed in the real environment, as detailed in section 2.4.

Steps – manual	Complementary Templates	Complementary Materials	Implementation
1. Manual to teach by challenges (Cover)			The methodology was applied in two classes (A and B) of a high school, with 46 students (each class consisted of 23 students) aged 15 to 16 years old. The topic 'Dynamics of the Earth' of the subject 'Biology and Geology' was addressed.
2. Before you begin - Explanation			
3. Before you begin - Tips			
4. Before you begin - Table of Contents			
5. Pose the challenge by teacher	CreaChallenges		The challenge selected by the teacher was 'How could we protect sensitive cities from natural catastrophes?' This topic connects with the student reality, and it is a social topic.
6. Planning	CreaPlanning		Each class participated in six sessions of fifty minutes each, spread over two weeks, and in both classes, the students were divided into groups of four to five.
7. Create teams	CreaTeams		
8. Presentation of the challenge to the class	CreaCloud		1st Session: The teacher placed on the blackboard relevant news related to the challenge. For example: "Baumgartner's space jump", "Fukushima", or "A kilomeric crack in Africa". Through a collaborative work, dynamic students expressed what they knew or what inspired them in each news item. Then, the teacher delved into the explanation and linked the news with the theory. Later, each group worked with one of the news stories, using the supplementary material: stickers, question examples, large sheets, etc. Finally, students were encouraged to search at home for more theoretical information related to the news item.
9. Research - theoretical and field research	CreaResearch		
10. Research - observation			
11. Research - interview			2nd Session: In their groups, the students put together the information gathered individually. Later, they synthesized the information by creating mind maps. The teacher controlled the time, offered feedback to the groups, and fostered students' motivation by using the supplementary material (stickers with comments, likes, questions, etc.)
12. Synthesize information			
13. Synthesize information - mind map	CreaMindMaps		3rd and 4th Sessions: Each group presented to the whole class their findings. After each presentation, the teacher completed the explanation with more theoretical information and corrected any mistaken information
14. Synthesize information - storyboard	CreaStoryboards		
15. Selection	CreaSelection		
16. Ideation	CreaIdeas		5th Session: In order to search for solutions to the challenge, students carried out design techniques (brainstorming and a 6-3-5) using materials included in the methodology. Meanwhile, the teacher measured the times and provided feedback.
17. Ideation - brainstorming	CreaIdeas		
18. Ideation - brainwriting method 6-3-5	CreaIdeas		
19. Definition of the concept	CreaConcept		6th Session: Based on the previous work, each group ideated and designed a concept solution. Afterwards, each group presented its concept to disseminate the results to their classmates. The class then discussed the advantages and disadvantages of each concept. Then, each student completed individually the self-assessment form included in the kit. Finally, by the teacher's choice, an exam was administered. The exam, together with the rest of the evaluation tools defined in Table 3, permitted us to corroborate the findings after applying the methodology.
20. Prototype	CreaPrototypes		
21. Self-evaluation - feedback	CreaEvaluation		
22. Dissemination			

	Integrate		Paper		Credential
	Prepare		Marker		Timer
	Apply in the classroom		Post-it		Notebook
	Assess		Sticker		Case

Fig. 4. Scheme of steps, kit materials, and implementation

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247 **2.4 Assessment**

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249 TCL was designed and developed following an iterative process in which we situated two separated
 250 assessments with different objectives and strategies, following the Xassess evaluation methodology
 251 (Blanco et al., 2016). We selected Xassess because it is a validated evaluation method centred in
 252 multidisciplinary teams, that offered several advantages, e.g. it can be easily adapted to the context;
 253 considers the assessment from the initial stages of the project; merges qualitative and quantitative
 254 approaches; and includes the vision of all the disciplines involved in the project. Xassess poses three
 255 evaluation strategies: (1) ‘complementation’ (each product dimension is evaluated with one
 256 qualitative or quantitative technique), (2) ‘triangulation’ (each dimension is evaluated with two or
 257 more parallel techniques), and (3) ‘combination’ (each dimension is evaluated with two or more
 258 successive techniques). In this study, we followed strategies of both complementation and
 259 combination of mixed methods. Tables 2 and 3 illustrate the general and detailed overview of
 260 evaluation objectives, strategies, and dimensions. We conducted the assessment in accordance with
 261 relevant ethical guidelines (Lodico et al., 2010), providing a verbal explanation and obtaining written
 262 consent from the participants (parental consent was obtained for participants under 18 years old).

263

264 **Table 2**

265 *Evaluations and General Objectives*

	Mid-term Evaluation	Second Evaluation (after TCL redesign)
Objectives	The objective was to validate the initial methodology idea and clear design doubts in a controlled environment, in order to redesign a final version of TCL.	The objective was to validate the whole methodology in a real environment, with end users (both students and teachers) and no time constraints in material preparation.
Strategies	Qualitative methods in a complementary relationship (each TCL dimension was evaluated with an evaluation method).	Combinatorial strategy of mixed methods, qualitative and quantitative (each TCL dimension was evaluated with several evaluation methods that complement each other).

266

267 The first evaluation was carried out within the development process of TCL. We selected a sole but
 268 significant user, as an ‘expert in the field’ (in line with the User-Centred Design premises), who
 269 provided a triple vision: as a teacher, as a professional in teacher training, and as a proxy of other
 270 users, the students. The prototype (Figure 2) was presented to the user by the evaluator, in a large
 271 room with a warm atmosphere. The user was asked to handle the TCL kit in order to raise a use case
 272 related to one of the subjects she was teaching at the moment. She utilised the methodology kit,
 273 reviewing the theoretical bases and designing the educational activities for the classroom, while the
 274 evaluator observed in a non-intrusive manner. At the end, we discussed barriers and enablers in a
 275 semi-structured interview, placing a special emphasis on the TCL adequacy to curriculum objectives.
 276 We called this discussion the ‘Theoretical curriculum review’ (see Table 3).

277

278 After having redesigned the methodology from the mid-term evaluation results (see Section 3), the
 279 second evaluation took place in a real educational environment with end users (teachers and
 280 students). The framework was set in two classes (A and B) of a high school, with a total sample of 48
 281 people: 46 students (each group consisted of 23 students) aged 15 to 16 years old, and two teachers
 282 with different profiles: main teacher (MT) and trainee teacher (TT). We considered teachers as the
 283 first level users because they interpret and apply the methodology, while the students represented the
 284 end user who benefits from the methodology implementation.

285

286 In the assessment procedure, TCL was mainly managed by the TT, less experienced, but having
 287 knowledge and sensitivity in new methodologies; the MT acted as supervisor, from his extensive
 288 experience in the centre and with students, and as quantitative evaluator of the students'
 289 achievement. Finally, a team of three technical evaluators conducted and assessed the whole process.
 290

291 In this second evaluation, the TT used the TCL kit autonomously from the beginning, planning and
 292 determining the activities by himself, while the evaluators acted as a support team and observers.
 293 The TT read cards, completed templates, and selected the support material, considering restrictions
 294 regarding the subject topic, time, space, number of students, and students' skills. Subsequently,
 295 methodology was implemented in the classroom (see Figure 4), being overseen by the TT.
 296

297 Starting from the Blanco et al. (2016) theoretical assessment framework, we adapted our evaluation
 298 strategy to the idiosyncrasy of the education scenario, focusing on the collaborative analysis offered
 299 by the different perspectives (the external vision from the three technical evaluators specialised in
 300 engineering design; the fresh and involved vision from the TT; and the experienced and objective
 301 vision from the MT).
 302

303 Table 3 shows how, why, and by whom each creativity factor was evaluated, including indicators,
 304 resources, and techniques applied during the experimentation, as well as the actors and scenarios
 305 involved. Although the phases were consecutive, the table assembles every dimension, regardless of
 306 whether they correspond to the first or second evaluation phase.
 307

308 **Table 3**
 309 *Objective, Indicators, and Evaluation Tools*

Creativity factors	Evaluation objective	Perspective	Indicator	Technique
1. Incorporation 10. Flexibility	<u>Incorporation and adaptation to the environment and curriculum</u>	Teachers	TCL adequacy to the curriculum objectives	Theoretical curriculum review, identifying proposed kit consistency
			Methodology's flexibility to be adapted to the topic	Observation and field notes (while teacher uses the tool); Semi-structured interview
			Difficulties detected when adapting it	
2. Practicality 3. Novel	<u>Material suitability</u>	Teachers	Teacher acceptance/perspectives about the methodology, manual, and resources.	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions; Semi-structured interview
			Opinion about design techniques	Semi-structured interview
			Interest in using the methodology	
			Analysis material usage by students	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions
		Student	Student acceptance/perspectives about the methodology	Survey (closed question)
	Comparison to other materials used in classes	Survey (closed and open question)		
4. Atmosphere 9. Participation	<u>Warm atmosphere and participation</u>	Teachers	Increased participation and communication, compared to other classes	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions; Semi-structured interview
			Dialogue between teacher-student, student-student, student-teacher	
			Students' attitudes analysis	
		Student	Perception of how they felt during class	Survey (closed question)
	Opinion about the atmosphere	Survey (closed and open question)		

			Perception about participation level	Survey (closed question)
			Participation level in the classroom compared to other classes	Survey (closed and open question)
5. Stimulation. 8. Intrinsic motivation 9. Participation	<u>Students' motivation.</u>	Teachers	Students' participation level, questions, opinions compared to other classes.	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions; Semi-structured interview
			Students' interest analysis in the classes	
			Amount of information collected by students	
			Comparison with other classes and previous works	
		Student	Interest aroused by classes	Survey (closed question)
			Attitude and disposition	
			Students' motivation to solve challenges and activities	
			Related concepts with their lives	
6. Analysis 11. Uncertainty	<u>Knowledge acquisition</u>	Teachers	Students' level in Geology	Semi-structured interview
			Learning concepts different to memory	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions
			Students' marks	Group work qualitative-quantitative evaluation Final exam
			Evolution of students' marks.	
		Student	Student perception about learning Geology	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions Group work and final exam
			Geology concepts understanding	
7. Cooperation	<u>Teamwork</u>	Teachers	Communication, coordination, and commitment among the members	Semi-structured interview
		Student	Team spirit	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions
			General opinion about teamwork	Survey (closed and open question)
			Opinion about own team (2 good aspects and 1 to improve)	Sheet 'CreaEvaluation'
			Opinion about other teams (2 good aspects and 1 to improve)	
13. Divergence	<u>Divergence</u>	Teachers	Amount of students' ideas	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions; Semi-structured interview
			Ideas analysis	
			Relation between ideas and the topic	
		Student	Students' perception about the quality of ideas	Sheet 'CreaEvaluation'
12. Time	<u>Think time</u>	Teachers	Relationship between reflection time and work	Semi-structured interview
14. Self-evaluation 15. Redefinition	<u>Self-evaluation and redefinition</u>	Teachers	Teachers' feedback (likes, comments, etc.) quality and quantity	Observation and field notes; Periodic internal discussions; Semi-structured interview
		Student	Opinion about own work within the team (2 good aspects and 1 to improve).	Sheet 'CreaEvaluation'
	<u>General opinion about methodology</u>	Teachers	General opinion about classes and methodology	Semi-structured interview
			Suggestions to improve the methodology	Semi-structured interview
		Student	Use of the methodology in other subjects	Survey (open question)
			Know what they liked most and least	

311 The techniques shown in Table 3 were chosen from those described in the literature (Lodico et al.,
312 2010), in accordance with each of the 15 indicators, and were classified under two perspectives:
313 teacher and student. Likewise, the selection of methods was based on the time available, the number
314 of users, and the teachers' previous experience.

315
316 During application of the methodology in the classroom, the teachers (TT and MT) acted as
317 evaluators in the field, conducting 'observation' and taking 'field notes' in a non-intrusive manner.
318 To facilitate this process, a guide that included key concepts to be observed was provided to the
319 teacher (TT). This guide had questions particularised for each activity, including: Has the class been
320 interesting to the students? Have the students experienced difficulties? Have the students been
321 involved? Have they collaborated as a team? Have they been motivated? How much time have they
322 invested?

323
324 All these observations were shared in 'periodic internal discussions' between the teachers (TT and
325 MT) and the three technical evaluators. In these discussions, the teachers acted as users, that is, as
326 participants assessed by the technical evaluators. Overall, six periodic internal discussions of 40
327 minutes each were conducted. In each session, one of the technical evaluators guided the group and
328 inquired about the specific indicators shown in Table 3. After each of these sessions, the three
329 technical evaluators met to discuss the conclusions obtained, which are considered in Section 3.

330
331 After the TCL application in class and to gain the teachers' perspectives, one of the technical
332 evaluators conducted a 'semi-structured interview' with TT and MT, in which the voice was
333 recorded. The interview included questions and comments such as: What perception do you have
334 about design and creativity? How would you define the material used during the classes? How would
335 you define students' attitudes during the classes? In order to avoid bias that evaluators may
336 introduce, the formulation of the questions was carefully examined, trying not to affirm
337 preconceptions of the researchers, and prevent the Hawthorne effect, that is, the tendency to the
338 positive response of the interviewees due to the special treatment they receive from the evaluator
339 (Adair, 1984; Diaper, 1990). The interviews were transcribed and coded according to the thematic
340 analysis approach (Patton, 2014) and using the objectives shown in Table 2 as themes. The full
341 transcriptions were sent to the teachers for review (Merriam, 1988) and were read several times
342 separately by each of the three technical evaluators. Afterwards, the researchers discussed their
343 reflections; in this discussion, the evaluators agreed to justify their suggestions with verbatims and to
344 avoid inserting their judgments, directions or beliefs without data from the conducted research. Once
345 a consensus was reached, the latent content and implicit messages of each theme were described in
346 the results section.

347
348 Additionally, to gather students' experiences and opinions, we used several techniques. 'Survey'
349 included several closed and open items and Likert scales to obtain perceptions on the assessment
350 objectives. The survey included questions and comments such as: Have you found a difference with
351 the materials used in other classes? Why? Have you felt motivated when solving the activities and
352 challenges posed? Then, the students completed the self-assessment form, namely 'sheet
353 CreaEvaluation'. Each student reflected and wrote about their work, the work of their team, and the
354 work of another group. The self-assessments were coded by one of the technical evaluators, who
355 grouped similar reflections. Additionally, we administered an exam. To analyse the students'
356 knowledge acquisition, the teachers (MT and TT) discussed the results of the group work and the
357 final exam. All these evaluation tools permitted us to extract the findings described in Section 3.

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359

360 **3. Results**

361

362 The mid-term evaluation with the mentioned expert user was aimed to improve its quality before its
 363 application in the classroom and involved changes in TCL. The expert user stressed the importance
 364 of the writing to improve its adaptation to the educational environment, replacing design language
 365 for educational language – for example: ‘Use “content” and “competence” instead of “objective”’.
 366 The teacher does not work with the “objective” but works with “content” or “competence”. She
 367 emphasised the need to use direct language with clear instructions: ‘Summarise paragraphs; write
 368 directly and in a more informal manner (...); use more icons to make the methodology more
 369 accessible. The end goal then, was to reword certain sentences and improve the graphic content.
 370 Specifically, some cards and templates were redesigned, since she commented that they could
 371 generate confusion or mistrust. For example, she wrote, ‘In the planning template, I have to code and
 372 create the plan myself (...); however, the template should indicate how to achieve this task. Many
 373 teachers do not know what resources to use to plan their classes (...) they use a textbook, not because
 374 it is the best material, but because it is guided’. She also determined the need to include new
 375 templates: ‘I propose to include an agreement sheet at the beginning. In my classes, students sign an
 376 agreement or contract to have a specific role. This contract increases their participation, assuming
 377 their responsibility’. Finally, she stressed the importance of paying more attention to some less-
 378 contemplated factors, such as ‘redefinition’: ‘We are not ensuring that the teacher redefines. It seems
 379 obvious that the teacher reviews and provides feedback to the students, but believe me, it is not’.
 380 Therefore, feedback stickers were included so that the teacher could write comments and ‘likes’, and
 381 the students could annotate their doubts in situ.

382

383 The collaborative analysis (between the three technical evaluators and the teachers) of all the
 384 evaluation layers, mid-term evaluation and second evaluation, gave rise to the results shown in Table
 385 4, presented in sections corresponding to the evaluation objectives collected in Table 3.

386

387 **Table 4**

388 *Assessment Results*

Objective	Teachers perspective	Students perspective
<u>Material Suitability</u>	Material quality was considered by teachers as a key element for the success of the tool. They claimed the materials were suitable. They valued positively the design discipline importance for materials development: <i>‘This material increases student curiosity and participation. (...) the results would not have been the same. Things are not only what you say, but how you say them’</i> (TT). In addition, the MT confirmed, <i>‘The material employed has been key, and students noticed the difference with respect to the materials of other classes’</i> . However, when teachers used the methodology materials, they detected the possibility of including previous teacher training: <i>‘The guide templates are great and very important, but I think that previous training on design and methodology would be beneficial’</i> (expert user).	Students valued the methodology very positively, although ‘simple’ is the factor they punctuated as the lowest (Table 5), and they judged the methodology as demanding. Most (85.2%) considered there to be a difference with the materials used in other classes. <i>‘It is more didactic, innovative, and practical than others. We are not used to work like that’</i> .

Table 5

Survey Results for the Question Related to ‘Material valuation’; Likert Scale from 0-10.

Average results. 95% Confidence interval.

Warm Atmosphere and Participation

Both teachers considered that the atmosphere during the lessons was pleasant thanks to the activities, fostering the good attitude of students: *'Participation has been much more favourable and frequent than normal'* (MT). This was reflected in most of the sessions. For example, during the brainstorming (Figure 5a) participation was very high in both classes. The students were comfortable and used informal assertions, opinions, and drawings: *'It would not be cool to be there when it (the natural catastrophe) happened'*, talking about geology concepts. Both teachers were surprised: while they expected noise and disturbance, students were calm, respected their classmates, and paid attention to everyone.

The majority of students (81.5%) confirmed they had participated more than usual. *'It wasn't a normal class, so we were more open to participate. Everybody has participated in everything'*. This was confirmed by the statistics (with an average score of 7.4 in the participation level of each student, and an 8 in the classmates' participation level) and by the teachers' testimony. All students confirmed the suitability of the learning atmosphere. 'Comfortable' is the most used adjective, followed by 'satisfied' and 'motivated'. The three main factors detected by them were: the teamwork, the activity's nature (enjoyable and entertaining), and the teachers' work and attitude. *'I really liked such a different way of teaching, your closeness, and how you valued our work. Thank you'*.

Students' Motivation and Interest for the subject

Both teachers agreed that motivation of students was constant throughout the sessions. The MT stressed the improvement over other classes. Among other examples, during the first session (Fig. 5a), *'Their questions evidence that they find [the material] stimulating (...) since the Geology subject is not usually very attractive'* (MT); in the second session (Figure 5b), *'They synthesised the information with mind maps, speaking, drawing, using attractive materials'*; in the fifth session (Figure 5c), *'When they used the 6-3-5 methodology, they were very focused and interested'* (TT). A clear indicator is the interest shown outside the classroom. TT stressed, *'Even during the weekend, students worked and shared information on Drive'*. Likewise, he met casually with a group of students attending an outside event related to geology; he added, *'This was really striking'*.

81.5% of students declared they felt more motivated than in other classes: *'I liked the enthusiasm and the effort I had in doing the activities'*. This agrees with the teachers' observations. In the survey, they were asked to describe their mood before the class started; most chose 'happy' (48%), followed by 'entertained' (22%) and 'bored' (15%). During the class, 63% affirmed to be 'entertained', followed by 'glad' (15%) and 'motivated' (11%); when the class finished, most of the students admitted to being 'happy' (48%), followed by 'motivated' (19%) and 'glad' (15%). It should be pointed out that two students chose 'bored' for all times, although they admitted being more motivated than in other classes. Also in accordance with teachers' observations, 44.4% of students affirmed that these sessions made the geology topic more interesting for them, and 51.2% found the subject related with some issues of their life. *'We have worked more dynamically in a boring subject, and now I see it as more interesting'*.

Knowledge acquisition

Results were good, but higher in Group A. For both teachers, the concepts were successfully understood, with a low failure rate (40 pass vs 6 fail) on the exam, while in the group work, all students passed (Table 6).

Table 6
Student Qualification Results (0-10).

	Group Work	Test	Final Mark
Group A	9.3 ± 0.5	7.9 ± 1.3	8.7 ± 0.8
Group B	8.1 ± 0.8	5.4 ± 2	7 ± 1.1

The qualitative results improve the statistic if we look at some of the students' reflections:
 - A different learning has been achieved: *'I have learned without studying too long with books; [I learned the subject] simply with research and listening'*.
 - Students' autonomy has been improved: *'I liked researching because I discovered data [and] curiosities...'*

<p><u>Teamwork</u></p>	<p>Both teachers detected differences between the groups. In Group A, all members worked adequately and equitably, while in Group B, not all students worked equally. Although the MT's opinion was, <i>'Students find it hard to organise teamwork; they are somehow inefficient'</i>, he also highlighted that they had worked better than in other activities: <i>'Their work has been better than I expected since the motivation here has been higher'</i>.</p>	<p>Most students (85.2%) also noticed a difference as a group and reflected upon the benefits obtained thanks to the interaction with their classmates: <i>'It is better than working alone because we all learn from each other' and 'My team has provided me knowledge and positive personal experiences'</i>. In addition, they recognised their commitment with the group, since the rest of the members depended on their work: <i>'My role as coordinator was essential to carry out the work'</i>. However, some students reported that not all classmates worked equally: <i>'I would like if all students were involved equally in all activities'</i>; this coincides with the teachers' perspective.</p>
<p><u>Divergence</u></p>	<p>The TT observed that students were restricted: <i>'They are guided day-to-day, and when they do something different, they find it hard to be proactive and creative'</i>. Equally, the TT added, <i>'The ideas that they chose to develop weren't the most amazing'</i>. The TT observed three reasons to justify this choice: greater ease, fear of failure, and less social influence in students who proposed it.</p>	<p>Students noted the importance of divergent thinking: <i>'It allows me to think more and differently about something'</i>. They also noted the importance of putting knowledge learned into effect: <i>'[It is necessary] not only to study but to put knowledge into effect and provide a solution (moderately possible) to a current problem'</i>. Solutions proposed were very diverse (Figure 5c): designing smart buildings and objects; ideas to stop the convection currents; research about the internal structure or traveling to the centre of the earth; and educational programs about emergencies were some of them.</p>
<p><u>Time constraints</u></p>	<p>The (short) times and the quickness of the activities were not a problem for the teachers. <i>'The stopwatch use has been very satisfactory; despite [the limited] time set, all students have finished the challenge since they have organised and adapted to the time proposed'</i> (TT).</p>	<p>Students offered two different stances:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There was a perception of lack of time for evaluated activities: <i>'I would like to have more classes to make the presentation better and to summarise the test content'</i>. - When they do not associate their work with a mark, they sense the quickness as beneficial: <i>'I liked having little time because it was spontaneous, and the classes weren't long or boring; I was very focused'</i>.
<p><u>Self-evaluation</u></p>	<p>There was a special emphasis on the need for clear, dynamic, and interactive presentations: <i>'There was very little fluency in the oral presentation; several students needed to read a sheet'</i> (TT).</p>	<p>Among the students, the perception of the need for improvement regarding their oral skills was also common: <i>'I would like to explain better, more easily, and without shame. I am not good at presenting'</i>. Some of them criticised the presentations when evaluating other groups: <i>'I would have liked to see clearer presentations with better explanations from my classmates'</i>.</p>
<p><u>General Opinion about Methodology</u></p>	<p>Both teachers agreed that the methodology is interesting, and they would like to use it in their classes to get students more involved. <i>'My opinion is tremendously positive (...) the task (.) is achieved very broadly. In addition, despite being applied to an unpopular</i></p>	<p>96% of students affirmed they would like to use this methodology in other classes: <i>'I wish we had the opportunity to work with this methodology, at least once a quarter'</i>. Even those initially sceptical recognised the validity of the method: <i>'I was afraid of the test because the class was practical, but in the end (...) I</i></p>

topic, very good results have been achieved' (TT). However, MT commented, 'Maybe it is insufficient to assimilate all the contents of the subject'. The expert user assured 'It is a demanding methodology for the student, since they must be fully active; thus, its use must be limited'.

learned the theory better'. However, a student noted the lack of traditional classes: 'I would like to have had theoretical classes to take notes and specify the content for the exam (...) [because] the activity was more general than the exam, which was more specific'.

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Fig. 5. (a) Investigation/brainstorming; (b) information synthesis; (c) ideation and concepts

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4. Discussion

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The results show that the proposed methodology and materials for its implementation achieve their objectives and contemplate the 15 creativity factors of Table 1. It can be asserted that applying the methodology in the classroom has advantages for students and teachers: it boosts competence learning, fosters research and participation, facilitates putting knowledge learned into effect, and allows for knowing new techniques. Therefore, the experience validates the methodology's utility in the schools.

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To frame the value of our results, it is interesting to analyse how other tools achieve the creativity factors in comparison to TCL. To accomplish this, we collected a total of eight representative tools from the educational field. We selected tools that 1) have a pedagogical basis similar to TCL; 2) seek learning through a different process than copying, memorisation, or reproduction; 3) are straightforward and easily adaptable; and 4) are easily accessible. The selected tools were presented to the three technical evaluators; individually, they reviewed each material and rated how each tool achieved the creativity factors. The authors then shared and discussed their assessments. By consensus, they determined to value each tool using a colour code in three levels: the resource considers the factor clearly (green), the resource considers the factor slightly (yellow), and the resource does not consider the factor (red). The indicators were reduced only to these three levels with the aim to ensure objectivity, assessing what could be observed in the available material of each proposal.

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In this manner, Figure 4 shows the extent to which TCL and the other representative resources satisfy each creativity factor. As mentioned, each factor is associated with a number according to the hypothetical sequence of use of these resource types in class. The comparison allows us to display which stages are most and least represented.

Fig. 6. Material analysis according to the creativity factors

As shown in Figure 6, the first half of factors is considered in the majority of cases. This seems logical, since they are key premises to apply this resource type in the classroom, related to the adaptation to the curriculum, the material characteristics, and the break of monotony. However, the factors related to the use of tools in the classroom and with the specific contributions to the students are less considered. Although they are fundamental for creativity promotion, the participation, divergence, and uncertainty factors are not worked enough; and self-evaluation, key in reflection and enrichment, is not entirely considered in any of the cases. It should be noted that Challenge-Based Learning (CBL) (Apple, 2011) has a lot in common with our proposal, meeting almost all factors. However, CBL lacks one of the essential bases in any educational material, which is practicality. It is true that CBL has a theoretical base more extensive and profound than other tools; however, it lacks the materials that favour and simplify its direct application in the classroom, such as kits, templates, complementary objects, and the like.

In TCL, all detected factors were kept in mind from its inception, but in the evaluation process, aspects to improve were detected (yellow squares in Figure 4). The assessment process, conducted from the method Xassess, allowed the evaluation from the beginning of the project, as well as the collaborative assessment between different disciplines. Applying Xassess supposed a multidisciplinary challenge at all levels, considering teachers as users and also as members of the team, thus co-designers. This permitted the drawing of deep and structured conclusions, giving rise to key contributions at a methodological level. These are presented below organised upon the assessment objectives; some of them can be useful to improve the methodology; others can allow for the creation of new resources and new teaching methods to improve students' creativity.

446

447 **Incorporation and adaptation to the environment and curriculum:** To guarantee its feasibility in
448 the classroom, any educational resource should start from these two premises. According to Blanco
449 et al. (2016), the x-disciplinary perspective to which we attended favoured the factors' compliance
450 and allowed us to adapt the methodology to the real environment. The results evidence it, both in the
451 teachers' views and in the students' marks. It is also important to highlight the value of TCL in the
452 more and more relevant competencies-based educational approach (Blanco et al., 2017) and its
453 weight for students' future employment and role in society (Tuning, 2003): it broadens the scope of
454 normally addressed competencies and enhances students' soft skills. However, it is undeniable that
455 to use this methodology requires an extra effort on the part of the teachers. They must consider: first,
456 the preparation of the materials, since the teacher should understand and plan the methodology; then,
457 the development of classes, where the teacher is in an unknown situation; and finally, the assessment
458 of the results, about which the expert user commented, '*Evaluating the transversal competences of
459 each student is not a direct task; it proves a challenge*'. Likewise, the difficulty of complying in time
460 and scope with the curriculum, as well as the lack of specific training, could make the application of
461 this methodology difficult. To face this challenge, we are now working on specific material to train
462 and involve the teacher in the use of TCL, which will contribute also to the teacher's professional
463 development.

464

465 **Material suitability:** Design influence on methodology and materials was found relevant and
466 positive. One of the main objectives of Design Thinking and design development processes is to
467 adapt the materials both to the context and to the different users, adding connotative and denotative
468 value. Students' cumulative opinion about the material was positive, although it should be noted that
469 some students did not describe it as a simple process '*some activities were really laborious*'. This is
470 understandable, considering that the student must be fully active and participative, far from the
471 passive stance adopted in the traditional methodology (Lee & Erdogan, 2007; McMullan, 2016;
472 Nguyen et al., 2017; Qi, 2017; Zhang & Guo, 2017; Zhao & Meng, 2015) to which they were
473 habituated. Thus, as well as for teachers, TCL constitutes a demanding methodology which requires
474 an extra effort on the part of students, but it also offers them important advantages. Despite these
475 benefits, as the expert user commented, '*TCL usage should be limited*'. On another level, it should be
476 considered that, nowadays, new technologies offer stimulating possibilities to create and share ideas
477 and content (Henriksen et al., 2016; Lombardi, 2007) and link well to the students' and teachers'
478 reality. This idea was supported by the TT, who asked, '*Have you considered the digital option? A
479 teacher could do this with a tablet*'. It suggests that technology inclusion could make a difference in
480 the methodology materialisation, which would be a significant improvement.

481

482 **Warm atmosphere and participation:** In TCL, one of the teachers' tasks is to bridge the division
483 between teacher and students, so that the students relax and get involved in the activities in an
484 uninhibited way. The methodology endeavoured to establish a comfortable climate based on trust
485 and communication between teacher-student and student-student by different means: students and
486 teachers used the material as a communication tool; the teacher was also asked to motivate the
487 students with certain messages ('nothing is wrong', for example) and attitudes. And this type of
488 relationship and dialogue brings significant benefits to students; as different authors assert, an
489 adequate psychosocial environment boosts a didactic environment that promotes and encourages
490 students to interact and participate with opinions, questions, and answers, increasing their academic
491 learning (Thapa et al., 2013; Vass, 2017; Voelkl, 1995), and offering identity, security, familiarity,
492 autonomy, and liberty (Thapa et al., 2013; Voelkl, 1995). Nevertheless, the atmosphere is affected by
493 the duration of the sessions: '*Creating the right climate takes extra time and effort (...); when it is
494 achieved, it is a pity to stop the class*'. Additionally, it is significant that the experience made the

495 students appreciate the teachers' work, as seen in the students' comments. Therefore, we can affirm
496 that, to some extent, the image of the teachers is improved, and the respect between students and
497 teachers is fostered. This is a relevant point because one of the most repeated conflicts in society is
498 that teachers are sometimes devalued in their work (Fort & Plaza, 2015).

499
500 **Students' motivation:** The results also evidence a high student motivation and interest during the
501 activities. TCL permits a proactive learning environment, fostering investigation and
502 experimentation, and showing that posing problems as challenges increases the students' intrinsic
503 motivation, in line with López (2008) and Amabile (1998). This even leads them to quench their
504 curiosity outside the classroom, which is significant. However, in several moments, it can be
505 observed how students are concentrated on their own marks (test and presentations): *'How will the*
506 *exam be?'*. Thus, with this reflection in mind, we consider that the intrinsic motivation factor is
507 'slightly' fulfilled in our methodology (see Figure 6). This is a logical response to the established
508 system; we cannot run away from the whole reality, but, of course, we align with Sternberg & Lubart
509 (1997) and others about the necessity of devaluing the importance of marks as the first extrinsic
510 motivator.

511
512 **Knowledge acquisition:** Also related to motivation, the methodology generated curiosity and
513 attention for its materialisation and because students worked differently than in other classes. These
514 coincide with the first two steps of the Neuroeducation sequence (Figure 7) (Acaso, 2017). The
515 emotion came when the theory was linked to the real world. According to Gerver (2017), *'Great*
516 *teachers have the ability to connect the concepts with the students' lives. And when students care*
517 *about things, they learn them'*. We must not forget that the novelty of the material can play in our
518 favour, but the design of the methodology allows us to totally refresh the stimuli from one project or
519 subject to another. Additionally, the 'peer learning' (Topping, 2005) process is also evidenced since
520 other teams' presentations are perceived as a source of learning and skills acquisition. Students learn
521 from their classmates, seeing the different approaches and solutions that other groups have found for
522 the same issue.

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Fig. 7. Learning process according to Neuroeducation, adapted from Acaso (2017)

529 **Teamwork:** Teamwork is considered one of the key skills to access the professional world (Daly et
530 al., 2012; Tulsi & Poonia, 2015; Valero, 2018). We formed groups of four or five in accordance with
531 Fowler (1990) and Blanco et al., (2017), and we corroborated that it is an ideal number since they

532 were manageable groups where everyone was able to contribute, and in general, the opinions were
533 positive. The positive influence of the peer learning effect was achieved not only between groups but
534 also inside the groups' members, as we can see in the comments. However, the teacher should be
535 alert to help students work as a team, in terms of effectiveness, organisation, and bad attitude
536 prevention; for example, those students that take advantage of teamwork to avoid tasks: *'During the*
537 *investigation, a classmate did not search for information'*. Maybe it would be useful to include a
538 guide in the methodology for teaching students how to work in teams in terms of commitment (to
539 carry out the tasks), communication (to listen to different opinions), complementarity (to put things
540 in common), coordination (to reach agreements), and trust (to express their own ideas).

541
542 **Divergence:** TCL contributes to fostering the divergent thinking drawn from uncertainty, risk-
543 taking, and making mistakes, in line with Craft (2003). The teacher has an important role here as the
544 resources provider and director; in this sense, TCL provides him or her the opportunity to train
545 students on managing materials, tools, concepts, ideas, and structures, in line with what Feldhusen
546 and Treffinger (1985) and Gervilla (2003) claim. In the experience, we included some rules related
547 to the methods included in TCL; for example in brainstorming (avoid judgment and criticism, build
548 on the others' thoughts, address only a conversation at a time, note all ideas, use simple sketches,
549 etc.). However, we observed that, in some ways, the lack of practice restricted students, so allowing
550 them to make decisions for themselves was a major challenge. In this regard, TT remarked, *'They*
551 *constantly wanted my approval, despite the freedom offered during classes'*. The conclusions drawn
552 from the teachers were very enlightening: greater ease, fear of failure, and the social influence of
553 certain students could all play a limiting role. For these reasons, it can be said that TCL considers the
554 divergence factor slightly (see Figure 6).

555
556 **Time and self-evaluation:** TCL provides times in which the student evaluates his/her progress and
557 performance, in order to promote reflection about what they has learned. The most repeated thought
558 raised by the students themselves (and validated by teachers) is about the need for resources and
559 training to carry out an effective public presentation, another soft skill that is usually missing; *'I get*
560 *very nervous when I speak in public'*. Although the methodology contributes to practicing
561 presentations and to speaking in public, it does not include materials focused on learning this skill.
562 Thus, in future versions of TCL, it would be interesting to add resources to help in this competence
563 formation. Additionally, it is interesting to observe the double standards in some students'
564 perception, which unfortunately have to do with traditional systems based on extrinsic motivators. In
565 particular is the case of the times assigned to each task, perceived as insufficient or sufficient
566 depending on whether the student perceived this as related or not with a quantitative mark, sensing
567 the evaluation separate from learning. This is, of course, a tough matter, but we believe that the
568 adoption of methods such as the proposed could contribute to mitigate this phenomenon.

569
570 Some limitations need to be acknowledged, and further work needs to be conducted to address them.
571 First, the scope of this study is confined only to a small sample of high school students in a Geology
572 class, and the outcomes may not be fully generalisable to other disciplines and/or a broader
573 population. Second, it should be noted that the research techniques used are mostly qualitative. In
574 this type of research, the participants rely on their individual experience, memories, and
575 expectations, which prevents the study from achieving total objectivity, complete neutrality, and
576 biases the research to some extent (Ponterotto, 2005). Nonetheless, to minimise this effect and
577 provide greater credibility, as commented before, we assessed each indicator with different methods.
578 Third, the TCL application requires an extra effort on the part of the teacher, since they should act as
579 a coach, a provider of resources, and a designer, facing complex and varied challenges. Therefore,
580 the teacher needs to be familiar with new methodologies and Design Thinking or needs to be trained

581 in some of these areas. Fourth, in the same manner, TCL is a demanding methodology for the
582 student, since they must be fully active. Thus, the students' workload should be well-balanced, since
583 an overload could be detrimental for their learning and their perception of active methodologies. In
584 this regard, in order to enrich the students' experience and learning, further, and more ambitious,
585 research could be conducted, with longer sessions and more detailed activities. Finally, it should be
586 noted that the participants of this study were used to traditional methodology, such that
587 understanding and developing the concepts about design and creativity as problem-solving was a
588 complex task. Design and creativity introduce mess, divergence, and novelty in a defined,
589 convergent, and traditional environment. Thus, understanding and developing design and creativity
590 cannot be solved solely with the use of the proposed methodology, but TCL can be considered an aid
591 to introduce these concepts.

592

593 **5. Conclusions**

594

595 In this paper, we proposed the Think-Create-Learn (TCL) methodology aimed at fostering creativity
596 in the class through design. During the development of this methodology, we also contributed to the
597 identification of 15 factors to be considered in the creation of new resources that foster creativity as a
598 problem-solving skill. Thus, TCL is based on two pillars: the design thinking processes and these 15
599 factors.

600

601 In TCL, theory and practicality are balanced. It is embodied in a practical kit with several types of
602 resources. A manual of 22 guide cards explains to the teacher step-by-step how to use TCL in the
603 classroom. The templates make application of TCL theory easier, offering tools flexible enough to be
604 adapted to any subject and helping the teacher to manage uncertainty. Both the visual and the tactile
605 nature of every support material are crucial and contribute to the success of the tool.

606

607 TCL was assessed quantitatively and qualitatively in a real educational context with teachers and
608 students. The results of this assessment showed that the proposed methodology contemplated all the
609 key factors to enhance creativity, supporting the teacher's work, and fostering students' competency-
610 based learning. Thus, we can affirm that this methodology provides a good tool to aid scholars,
611 teachers, even designers to develop design and creativity.

612

613 This study also reflects the potential of applying Design Thinking in education. Design and creativity
614 are multidimensional and difficult to teach, so further studies are needed to support teachers in this
615 task. In this paper, we contribute to reaffirm (a) the need to create new resources for the development
616 of creativity in educational centres, (b) the relevant role that the design discipline could have, and (c)
617 the relevance of the 15 creativity factors to assess new proposal's effectiveness. Research in these
618 directions would enhance students' 21st century thinking skills.

619

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